

before seeding or at 24 hours before uprooting seedlings, or to the plants at the panicle initiation stage (see table).

Application of SBP 24 hours before the uprooting of seedlings delayed seedling establishment by 10 to 12 days. Its

application to the standing crop caused severe foliar damage due to phytotoxicity, and sharply reduced yields. ■

Sheath blight incidence in weed hosts

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The natural occurrence of sheath blight of rice caused by *Rhizoctonia solani* in 21 weed hosts was recorded in both kuruvai (Jun–Sep) and thaladi (Oct–Jan). The pathogen from diseased weed hosts in rice field bunds was isolated in rice agar medium and used to inoculate the susceptible variety ADT31. The development of symptoms was observed and the pathogen's identity confirmed.

Sheath blight occurred severely in *Eriochloa procera*, *Andropogon asper*, *Cynodon dactylon*, and *Ischaemum indicum* (see table). That indicates that the pathogen can perpetuate itself in weed hosts during the off-season. ■

Perpetuation of *R. solani* in weed hosts. Tamil Nadu, India.

Weed host	Family	Disease reaction ^a
<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm. f.	Commelinaceae	+
<i>Chionachne koenigii</i> (Spreng.) Thw.	Gramineae	+
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	+
<i>Digitaria longiflora</i> (Retz.) Pers	Gramineae	+
<i>Merremia emarginata</i> (Burm. f.) Hall. f.	Convolvulaceae	+
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	Gramineae	+
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	"	+
<i>Digitaria adscendens</i> (H.B.K.) Henr.	"	+
<i>Chloris barbata</i> Sw.	"	+
<i>Paspalidium flavidum</i> (Retz.) A. Camus	"	++
<i>Brachiaria mutica</i> (Forsk.) Stapf	"	++
<i>Fimbristylis ovata</i> (Burm. f.) Kern	Cyperaceae	++
<i>Desmodium triflorum</i> (L.) DC.	Papilionaceae	+++
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i> (L.) Beauv.	Gramineae	+++
<i>Urochloa panicoides</i> Beauv.	"	+++
<i>Alysicarpus monilifer</i> Dc.	Papilionaceae	+++
<i>Dichanthium caricosum</i> (L.) A. Camus	Gramineae	+++
<i>Eriochloa procera</i> (Retz.) C.E. Hubb	"	++++
<i>Andropogon asper</i> Heyne	"	++++
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	"	++++
<i>Ischaemum indicum</i> (Houtt.) Merrill	"	++++

^a+ to ++++ = increasing intensity of disease reaction.

Carbendazim controls rice blast

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The systemic fungicide Bavistin 50 WP (carbendazim) and six other fungicidal chemicals were tested for control of rice blast disease in the variety Pusa 2-21. The field trials lasted for three seasons

at the Pattambi Rice Research Station.

The fungicides were sprayed 4 times at 2-week intervals starting at 14 days after transplanting. Neck blast counts were taken 10 days after the last spraying. The percentages of affected panicles were based on random observations of all tillers in 60 hills/plot.

Carbendazim gave the maximum reduction in neck blast and increase in

grain yield, followed by Hinosan and IBP (see table). ■

Control of rice blast by carbendazim (Bavistin 50 WP), Rice Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India.

Treatment ^a	Dose/ha	1976-77 rabi		1977-78			
		Neck blast (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Kharif		Rabi	
				Neck blast (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Neck blast (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Hinosan 50 EC	0.5 liter	37	1.2	64	2.6	26	2.3
Dithane-Z-78	2.0 kg	54	0.9	66	2.4	33	2.1
Dithane-M-45	2.0 kg	53	0.9	68	2.4	28	2.1
Difolatan	1.5 kg	52	0.9	70	2.4	33	2.1
Fytolan	2.0 kg	45	1.0	75	2.4	28	2.1
Bavistin 50 WP (carbendazim)	0.5 kg	21	1.2	45	2.9	14	2.5
Kitazin 48 EC	1.0 liter	42	1.1	66	2.4	27	2.2
Control		57	0.8	86	2.1	47	1.9
CD (0.05)		(7.74)	n.s.	(21.09)	0.392	(6.16)	n.s.

^aEC = emulsifiable concentrate, WP = wettable powder.

Identification of strains of *Corticium sasakii* in India

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Two isolates of *Corticium sasakii* – the sheath blight fungus – from rice (designated R) and from *Brassica campestris* var. *cunifolia* (designated B) with apparently different pathogenicity were studied at the Mycology Research Laboratory, Assam Agricultural University, Jorhat. At 14°C, the isolates on potato dextrose agar did not differ in growth rates, but at 21 and 36°C, they behaved differently. While the growth of R was greater at 21 than at 36°C, that of B did not differ at the 2 temperatures. B had a higher pH requirement than R. But when tested by the poisoned food technique the isolates did not differ in

reaction to two potential fungicides, methyl benzimidazole carbamate (MBC) and methoxyethyl mercury chloride (MEMC). MBC was more effective on both isolates.

No appreciable differences in

pathogenicity could be found between the isolates on soybean (highly susceptible to both), *Imperata cylindrica*, *Saccharum spontaneum*, and water hyacinth (less susceptible to both). But on *Colocasia antiquorum*, R did not

incite infection and B was virulent. Pusa 2-21 was highly susceptible to both isolates, but only B was virulent on IR8, IET3267, and RP4-41. It was concluded that the isolates constituted distinct strains. ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

New record of a rice leaf miner, *Pseudonapomyza asiatica* Spencer (Diptera: Agromyzidae), in the Philippines

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Observations on rice seedlings in Iloilo, Pangasinan, and Laguna provinces, Philippines, in 1977 and 1978 revealed the presence of an unknown leaf miner. The same leaf miner attacked both transplanted and direct-seeded rice.

The mines (10–42 mm long, and 1–4 mm wide) run parallel to the leaf

blade and usually occur at the apices. Each dissected leaf mine had a single white larva 0.80 to 2.00 mm long. The larva pupated within the mine, protected by the upper and lower epidermis of the leaf. The puparium, 1.35 mm long and 0.65 mm wide, appears mat, and each segment boundary is marked by 4 or 5 rows of irregularly placed spines. The puparium is generally glued firmly within the mine. Adult flies that emerged from infested leaves bearing pupae were identified as *Pseudonapomyza asiatica* Spencer by Dr. M. Sasakawa of Kyoto Prefectural University, Japan. The adults can be distinguished from related species by the bluntly angulate third antennal segment, mat mesonotum, grayish orbits, black lateral sides of thorax, largely colorless $M_1 + 2$ and $M_3 + 4$, and the squamae and fringe are conspicuously silvery white.

P. asiatica is widely distributed in Asia but this is the first account of its being a rice pest in the Philippines.

Another host, *Cynodon dactylon*, was reported in Singapore in 1961.

Pseudonapomyza atra has been mentioned as a leaf miner on rice in India and Taiwan, but according to taxonomists it is distributed in the temperate regions of North America and Europe. Therefore, the early records of *P. atra* in Asia probably referred to *P. asiatica*. ■

Spiders check planthopper population

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Spiders of different families have been reported to prey on the brown planthopper (BPH). Large numbers of spiders (av 2/hill) are seen on the rice crop, especially during later growth stages, near Kuttanadu, Kerala, where the BPH has become endemic. During a severe BPH incidence in the main punja season (Oct–Feb) field plots were treated with six insecticides. Six days after treatment, the populations of both BPH and spiders were lower than those in the untreated plots. Fifteen days after treatment the populations increased and the effect of insecticide treatment was not significant. During the next crop season (Apr–Sep), when insecticide application was negligible, the spider populations were high and the BPH population low.

These observations suggest that spiders are potential natural enemies of the BPH and that they can keep its population well below the economic threshold.

Photo 1. Rice leaves with damage (mines) and pupae of *P. asiatica*.

Photo 2. Adult fly of *P. asiatica*.

